

feeding could be the major reason for the shift in virus transmission efficiency.

At Los Baños, RTV incidence in IR54, IR64, and some other cultivars having Gam Pai 30-12-15 in their parentage was very low before the 1986

wet season (WS) and very high from 1987 dry season (DS) onward. RTBV + RTSV incidence on IR54 and IR64 was very low in 1986, but very high in 1988 (see table). Gam Pai 30-12-15 also had high incidence of RTBV + RTSV in

1988. These results indicate the breakdown of IR54 and IR64 resistance to RTV in Los Baños in 1987 DS was due to a shift in GLH virulence. RTBV + RTSV incidence on IR36 was high in 1986, but low in 1988 (see table). □

Resistance to bacterial leaf streak (BLS) in hybrid rice and parental lines

Li Ren-Hua, Hunan Hybrid Rice Research Center, Changsha, Hunan, China; and E. Medalla, Plant Pathology Department, IRRI

Five rice hybrids from IRRI and their male sterile (A) and restorer (R) lines were evaluated against two isolates of BLS in the greenhouse. Pregerminated seeds were grown in plastic trays, three rows in a tray, one for each F₁, A, and R lines.

Isolates 93 and 335 of *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzicola* were used to spray-inoculate the test plants at 21 and 30 d after sowing (DAS). The bacterial suspension was adjusted to 10⁹ cells/ml. Scoring was done 10 and 15 d after inoculation (DAI) using the *Standard evaluation system for rice* (SES), based on leaf area infection.

Reactions of different A and R lines and F₁ to BLS. IRRI, 1988.

Hybrid	Reaction ^a					
	Isolate 93			Isolate 335		
	A	R	F ₁	A	R	F ₁
IR46830A/IR50	7.2	4.9	7.7	2.5	2.2	3.8
	4.0	3.7	4.4	6.0	3.7	5.1
IR46830A/IR9761-19-1	8.0	8.9	8.5	5.2	6.1	4.9
	4.6	5.3	6.3	7.4	6.5	6.8
IR54752A/IR54	8.8	7.5	7.9	3.4	0.3	2.5
	3.8	2.4	3.2	5.0	3.7	5.7
IR54752A/IR19392-211-1	8.7	8.7	8.9	3.1	1.8	2.0
	3.1	4.8	4.3	5.2	6.0	6.3
Zhongshan 97A/Milyang 54	8.4		2.1	3.7		0.0
	6.2	0	2.0	7.5	0	2.7

^aScores are averages at 10 DAI on plants inoculated at 21 DAS (first row in each set), and 30 DAS (second row). 0-3 = resistant, 3.1-4.9 = moderately resistant, 5-9 = susceptible.

Of the five hybrids, Zhongshan 97A/ Milyang 54 was resistant to the two isolates in both inoculation stages (see table). IR46830A and IR54752A became moderately resistant when inoculated with isolate 93 at 30 DAS.

The two parental lines with moderate resistance produced rice hybrids with moderate resistance. The R line contributed resistance in F₁ for the A line-susceptible and R line-resistant combination. □

Sieve tube number in tungro (RTV)-infected rice plants

B. Srinivasulu and R. Jeyarajan, Plant Pathology Department, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Coimbatore, India

To study the effect of RTV infection on phloem tissues, we collected leaves from healthy and RTV-infected rice plants. Cross sections of leaves of the same age were dipped in a saturated solution of phloroglucinol in 18% hydrochloric acid. The phloem cells per microscopic field were counted.

We found no necrosis of phloem cells in infected leaves. However, the mean number of sieve tubes was 123 in healthy leaves, compared to 73 in diseased leaves. We conclude that RTV reduced sieve tubes 41%. □

Simplification of sampling method for assessing bacterial blight (BB) severity

N. Nilpanit, W. Sirisantana, and S. Disthaporn, Division of Plant Pathology and Microbiology, K. Soontrajarn, Rice Research Institute, Department of Agriculture, Bangkok, Bangkok 10900, Thailand

This study attempted to simplify methods to assess BB (*Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae*) severity. Rice variety RD9 was transplanted into 5 × 5 m² plots at Pathum Thani Rice Research Center, Thailand, during DS 1987. Disease was induced by inoculation in several levels on border rows of seven treatments with two replications each.

Severity was assessed 5 times at 49 d after transplanting (DT), 55 DT, 62 DT, 69 DT, and 76 DT, on 8 hills per plot. Leaf area damage on each of the top three leaves of each tiller (LAD1, LAD2, and LAD3) as well as whole hill damage (VLAD) were visually assessed and expressed in percent. The average leaf area damage of leaves 1-3 (ALAD) and disease incidence for each leaf position (IL1, IL2, IL3, and ILT) were calculated.

At maximum tillering (49 DT) and booting (55 DT) severity on the third leaf (LAD3) was highly correlated with average severity on the whole hill (ALAD) (see table). At flowering (62 DT), close correlations between average severity on a hill and severity on second or third leaves (LAD2 and LAD3) were found. At milk (69 DT) and dough

stages (76 DT), close correlations between average severity on a hill and the flag leaf (LAD1) or second leaf (LAD2) were observed. At all growth stages, incidence on all upper three leaves (ILT) was closely related to average severity on these leaves (ALAD).

Results suggest that BB severity can be assessed on one of the upper three leaves instead of on all three. The method could be further simplified by counting infected leaves, rather than by estimating leaf damage. □

Susceptibility of bacterial blight (BB) differential varieties of IRRI, Japan, and Korea in Nepal

P. B. Karki, D. N. Sah, and D. N. Manandhar, Agriculture Station, Parwanipur, Nepal

BB caused by *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae* (Xco) is a major rice disease in the terai and inner terai regions (main rice-growing area) of Nepal. Recently, this disease was observed also in the warm river basins of the hill regions. The numerous pathogenic races of Xco in Nepal hinder efforts to breed resistant varieties. To identify pathogenic variability of Xco, IRRI and Japanese varieties were tested as possible differentials at Parwanipur, Janakpur, and Kankai from 1979 to 1987.

Twenty-one-day-old seedlings of differential varieties were transplanted in 3 rows, each 5 m long. Each hill had 1 seedling and spacing was 20 × 20 cm. The plots were fertilized with NPK at 120-30-30 kg/ha. Plants were clip-inoculated at maximum tillering. The disease was scored 21 d after inoculation according to the IRRI *Standard evaluation system for rice*.

All IRRI varieties and Japanese differentials except DV85 in the 1979 test at Kankai were found susceptible to Nepalese isolates. The differential varieties have these resistance genes: Java 14, *Xa-1* and *Xa-3*; Kogyoku, *Xa-1* and *Xa-kg*; Nigeria 5, *Xa-1* and *Xa-2*; Tetep, *Xa-1* and *Xa-2*; IR20, *Xa-4*; IR1545-339-2-2, *xa-5*; DV85, *xa-5* and

Xa-7 Kuntlan, *Xa-6*; and CAS209, *Xa-10*. During 1979 tests, Korean differentials Milyang 23, Yushin, Suweon 281, and Tongil with resistance genes from Kinmaze, Kogyoku, Kogyoku, and Rantai-emas groups, respectively, were also nonfunctional against Parwanipur and Kankai isolates.

Thus, IRRI, Japanese, and Korean resistant varieties cannot be used as differentials to identify pathogenic races of Xco in Nepal. Therefore, national programs should develop their own differentials, possibly using local popular varieties, to monitor pathogenic variability of Xco. □

Insect resistance

Use of tissue culture to evaluate rice resistance to lepidopterous pests

P. Caballero, D. H. Shin, Z. R. Khan, R. C. Saxena, B. O. Juliano, and F. J. Zapata, IRRI

Larval development was evaluated on plant tissues cultured from rice genotypes varying in levels of insect resistance. Murashige and Skoog (MS) and Linsmaier and Skoog (LS) media were used to induce and develop callus. Each liter of MS medium was supplemented with 2 mg 2, 4-D, 1 mg BAP, and 30 g sucrose (MS3); and each

liter of LS medium, with 1 mg 2,4-D and 30 g sucrose. *Oryza ridleyi* and Rexoro calli were obtained on LS medium; Chianan 2, Yabami Montakhab 47, and IR5865-26-1 calli were obtained on MS3 medium.

In a no-choice bioassay, about 200 mg of callus were placed in a 5-cm-diameter Gelman 7242 petri dish (see figure). Rexoro and *O. ridleyi* were susceptible and resistant checks, respectively. Due to limitations in available callus, Chianan 2 was bioassayed only against *Scirpophaga incertulas*, Yabami Montakhab 47 against *Chilo suppressalis*, and Ptb 10 and IR5865-26-1 against *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis*. Insect egg masses were surface sterilized and incubated at 28 °C until eggs hatched. Callus in each petri

Lepidopterous pests reared on rice plant calli: a) *C. medinalis* larvae feeding on Ptb 10 callus; b) *S. incertulas* larva feeding on resistant *O. ridleyi* callus; c) growth of *C. medinalis* larvae on calli of *O. ridleyi* (c1), IR5865-26-1 (c2), Ptb 10 (c3), and Rexoro (c4); and d) growth of *C. suppressalis* larvae on calli of *O. ridleyi* (d1), Yabami Montakhab 47 (d2), and Rexoro (d3). IRRI, 1987-88.